

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Overcoming the mobility bias in transnational entrepreneurship

Ekaterina Vorobeva

The Research Centre for East European Studies, The Bremen International Graduate School of Social Sciences, The University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany

Correspondence

Ekaterina Vorobeva, The Research Centre for East European Studies, The University of Bremen, Room 3750, Klagenfurter Straße 8, D-28359, Bremen, Germany.
Email: vorobeva@uni-bremen.de

Funding information

ITN 'MARKETS', EU-MSCA, Grant/Award Number: 861034

Abstract

The current article contributes to the debates on immobility in migration studies. More specifically, it aims to show and challenge mobility bias in transnational entrepreneurship; the relevant scholarship appears to overconcentrate on immigrants as major driving forces of cross-border business relations while ignoring the contributions of nonmigrant populations. Based on the qualitative data collected from Central Asian migrant entrepreneurs in Russia, this research dispels the myth about the inertness of nonmigrants by demonstrating their utmost importance in establishing and sustaining transnational enterprises. Therefore, transnational entrepreneurship should be regarded as the result of joint efforts of both mobile and sedentary actors. The presented evidence suggests that mobility and immobility are integrally intertwined and mutually constitutive. This study calls for a more balanced and nuanced vision of how transnationalism occurs.

KEYWORDS

immobility, migrant entrepreneurship, mobility, transnational entrepreneurship, transnationalism

INTRODUCTION

With the rapid growth of interest in cross-border phenomena in the last 3 decades, transnational entrepreneurship has become a popular subject of academic and policy discussions. As shown by previous studies, a significant percentage of migrant entrepreneurs, ranging from 37.5% to 78.5%, are involved in transnational practices (Bagwell, 2018; Portes et al., 2002). Transnational entrepreneurship is broadly understood as the business activities of immigrants

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2022 The Authors. *Global Networks* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

that take place across national borders (Drori et al., 2009; Portes et al., 2002). Since they are simultaneously embedded in several markets, migrants can gain access to multilocal economic, human and social capital (Drori et al., 2009; Portes et al., 2002). Utilizing their transcultural competences and networks, migrant entrepreneurs may enjoy a 'first mover' advantage in the markets of their home states (Ojo, 2012).

However, despite the calls for a more inclusive perspective (e.g., Duan et al., 2021; Morawska, 2013; Sandoz et al., 2021), the transnational entrepreneurship scholarship displays a persistent mobility bias: it predominantly focuses on the agency of migrant entrepreneurs, putting aside the contributions of sedentary actors in enabling transnational entrepreneurship (Drori et al., 2009; Schewel, 2020). Indeed, business opportunity recognition, mobilization of cross-border networks, utilization of transnational capital and risk-taking were predominantly discussed as activities carried out solely by migrant entrepreneurs (Drori et al., 2009). This vision portrays the nonmigrant business partners of migrant entrepreneurs as being of secondary importance, passive and nonentrepreneurial (Stockdale & Haartsen, 2018).

The current study intends to debunk a widely held belief in the inertness of 'those left behind' and, therefore, to take a first step towards overcoming the mobility bias in relevant scholarship (Schewel, 2020). Based on 17 biographical interviews conducted with Central Asian (Uzbek, Kyrgyz and Tajik) transnational entrepreneurs in Russia, the current research demonstrates that sedentary actors play a crucial role in establishing and sustaining cross-border entrepreneurship. As the data show, they act as initiators of transnational business relations, bring in diverse capital, and bear the associated entrepreneurial risks. Therefore, this study propounds that transnational entrepreneurship should be understood as an outcome of the concerted and committed efforts of both mobile and nonmigrant actors. These findings suggest that mobile and sedentary populations engage in constant coshaping of each other's lives, pointing at the close interdependence between mobility and immobility.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Transnational entrepreneurship: Definitions and main debates

Recently, transnationalism has become an increasingly popular lens to explore emerging phenomena in a constantly globalizing world. One of the most commonly accepted definitions of transnationalism was proposed by Schiller et al. (1992, p. 1), who defined it as 'the processes by which immigrants build social fields that link together their country of origin and their country of settlement'. Therefore, by overcoming the national containers' bias, transnationalism serves to describe modes of being in a highly interlinked world; it is concerned with the emergence of new social, economic and political fields arising from individuals' simultaneous presence in and belonging to several countries. This new lens helped bring to light phenomena such as transnational practices, transnational belonging, transnational networks, transnational enterprises and transnational families. In this vein, highlighting the incompleteness of migrants' relocation to a host state, Carling et al. (2021) stated that transnationalism can be approached not only as a result of but also as an alternative to migration.

In a vast amount of relevant literature, transnationalism is characterized as a process enabled by civil society 'from below' (Tedeschi et al., 2020). Although almost anyone can engage in transnationalism, its key actors are believed to be primarily migrants. Therefore, the term 'transmigrant' has been coined to describe migrants who are involved in regular transnational practices such as traveling, remitting and networking, linking together their countries of origin and of residence. Through these activities, transmigrants create so-called transnational spaces, a new cross-border arena that they inhabit (Levitt & Schiller, 2004).

Transnational entrepreneurship has emerged to highlight the intersection of transnationalism and migrant entrepreneurship. Portes et al. (2002), Chen and Tan (2009) and Drori et al. (2009) characterize transnational entrepreneurship as an exclusively migrant-specific phenomenon; scholars have defined transnational entrepreneurs (TEs) as immigrant entrepreneurs who are embedded in more than one economic context. Thus, transnational

entrepreneurship, also referred to as transnational (im)migrant entrepreneurship (e.g., Duan et al., 2021), is a subfield within the broader migrant entrepreneurship scholarship (Chen & Tan, 2009). Drori et al. (2009, p. 1001) specify that 'the process of TE involves entrepreneurial activities that are carried out in a cross-national context and initiated by actors who are embedded in at least two different social and economic arenas'. However, as a note, Ambrosini (2012), Bagwell (2015) and Harima and Baron (2020) pointed out that transnationalism can be present in the entrepreneurial activities of migrants in multiple ways, from regular transnational travels to the utilization of transnational experiences. Therefore, the placement of transnational enterprises on the spectrum of embeddedness in the transnational economic field can vary widely; their cross-border activities 'may be extensive, or just occasional but still important to the business' (Bagwell, 2015, p. 334).

In the body of relevant literature, the question of the difference between international and transnational entrepreneurship has arisen. Both are interested in business activities that take place across national borders. However, drawing a distinction between the two may allow us to better specify their focuses. The distinction appears to lay in a key unit of analysis. In studies on transnational entrepreneurship, the figure of a migrant entrepreneur has become the main focus of inquiry. In contrast, international entrepreneurship is more concerned with the behaviour of firms, not enterprising individuals. Therefore, the personal histories of businesspersons, including migration experiences and their impact on business operations, fall out of its focus (Sandoz et al., 2021).

Transnational entrepreneurship introduces personal resources, traits and histories into the discussion on international entrepreneurship. This interest of transnational entrepreneurship in the figures of businesspersons can be partially attributed to the small number of migrant enterprises that are proven to be hugely dependent on the personal qualities of the founders and their networks (Pruthi et al., 2018). The multilocal embeddedness of migrant entrepreneurs is predominantly discussed as a positive fact: it allows them to take advantage of various forms of transnational capital (Bagwell, 2015; Drori et al., 2009). Cross-border networks and transcultural competencies facilitate migrants' easier access to investments, new ideas and the export and import of products and services (Bagwell, 2015; Duan et al., 2021; Honig, 2020). In regard to personal traits, TEs are often characterized by low risk aversion, high creativity and developed leadership skills (Yeung, 2002).

However, none of the resources of TEs have been discussed as extensively as their transnational networks, which consist of the contacts that migrants establish or mobilize across borders in search of suppliers, partners and capital (Brzozowski et al., 2017). Transnational networks have been metaphorically described as a 'diversity dividend', a competitive edge of migrant entrepreneurs in a host state (Bagwell, 2015; Chen & Tan, 2009; Sommer, 2020). First, they form major channels for the transfer of transnational capital. Previous studies have linked extensive transnational networks to easier access to new markets and cheap labour, higher sales, more effective knowledge transfer and innovations (Bagwell, 2015). Second, cross-border networks are believed to be the source of unique benefits such as opportunity recognition and motivation sustainment (Harima, 2014). Thus, by providing various forms of support, cross-border networks serve as 'informal business incubators' (Menzies et al., 2003, p. 125). Transnational networks predominantly, but not exclusively, refer to connections between host and home states (Brzozowski et al., 2014; Chen & Tan, 2009; Harima & Baron, 2020; Levitt, 2001).

Unveiling mobility bias in transnational entrepreneurship

The twin of mobility rather than its antipode, immobility has, nevertheless, only recently entered the migration debates (Erdal, 2021; Schewel, 2020; Schiller & Salazar, 2013). On the one hand, it served as a critique of the previously celebrated mobility turn, which tightly linked migration to loosely defined progress in both host and home states (Salazar & Smart, 2011). On the other hand, slightly before immobility gained momentum, an understanding of migration as a fragmented journey was formed in relevant scholarship (e.g., Collyer, 2007). Implying alternating moments of mobility and immobility, this vision of migration appears to have contributed to the growing interest in sedentary ways of being (Erdal, 2021). Some scholars have called for scholarly attention to be shared between mobility and immobility

(e.g., Erdal, 2021; Schiller & Salazar, 2013). Thus, resolving the dichotomy between 'roots' and 'routes', this new focus intends to bring immobility back into the debates without adopting a sedentary bias, a normalization of stasis (Erdal, 2021).

These latest developments highlight a strong mobility bias in migration studies understood as 'an overconcentration of theoretical and empirical attention on the determinants and consequences of mobility and, by extension, the concomitant neglect of immobility' (Schewel, 2020, p. 331). Indeed, focusing entirely on mobility and its agents, that is, immigrants, appears to be insufficient for explaining migration processes (Schewel, 2020). The agency, perspectives and experiences of nonmigrants, while often ignored, are crucial for improving our knowledge of migration-related phenomena (Salazar & Smart, 2011).

Due to its primary concern with enterprising migrants, transnational entrepreneurship seems to be especially inclined to fall victim to mobility bias. It is precisely TEs' social location at the intersection of several proactive roles, namely, a transmigrant and an entrepreneur, that magnifies the importance of their agency. Similar to the definition of a transmigrant, a general definition of an entrepreneur highlights the proactive behaviour of an 'actor who recognizes entrepreneurial opportunities and makes moderately risky decisions with a view to innovating' (Filion, 2021, p. 80). Yeung (2002, p. 30) defines 'transnational entrepreneurs as businesspersons who take specific proactive action to overcome inherent problems and difficulties associated with international business activities'. With the spread of the belief in the capacity of entrepreneurship to solve many economic problems, such as unemployment and limited economic growth, migrant entrepreneurs have been regarded by academics, policy-makers and the media as 'distinctive agents of change' (Chen & Tan, 2009). Businesspersons with migrant backgrounds are often portrayed as '(1) leaders, (2) innovators, (3) disrupters, (4) managers, (5) risk takers, (6) inventors, (7) idea generators, (8) creators of new organizations' (Honig, 2020, p. 1976). They establish networks, introduce new products and practices, optimize resources, leverage experience, promote international trade, innovate, develop new strategies and identify and exploit business opportunities (Drori et al., 2009; Lundberg & Rehnfors, 2018; Sinkovics & Reuber, 2021).

These statements imply that TEs play a central role in the facilitation of transnational entrepreneurship. They make important contributions to cross-border business cooperation primarily, but not exclusively, by initiating transnational business relations and bearing risk. First, initiation happens through opportunity recognition, mobilization of cross-border networks and utilization of transnational capital (Drori et al., 2009; Lundberg & Rehnfors, 2018). Migrant entrepreneurs are believed to generate ideas for cross-border businesses, to reach out to their compatriots in home states and lead the process of transnational enterprises' establishment and development. Second, several studies suggest a positive relationship within the triangle of migration experience, entrepreneurship and low-risk aversion (e.g., Batista & Umblijs, 2014; David et al., 2021; Honig, 2020). Therefore, being 'self-selected risk takers' (Honig, 2020, p. 1976), migrants are considered to be especially inclined to bear risks, including those for the establishment of transnational enterprises (David et al., 2021). Yeung (2002, p. 39) states that for TEs, 'this risk-taking is particularly critical because operations in a foreign land are often filled with uncertainties and potential business risks'.

However, any transnational relation is a two-way street; a migrant as well as a nonmigrant may potentially act as an initiator of this relationship. Although transnational entrepreneurship scholarship originally aimed to highlight the role of mobility in entrepreneurship, which was ignored by other business studies, it failed to acknowledge the diversity of actors involved in transnational economic processes. As a result, the role of nonmigrants in establishing and maintaining transnational business ties has been noticeably overlooked. This can be partially attributed to the image of nonmigrants existing in the general and academic discourses. Indeed, in the relevant literature, nonmigrants have received labels with pronounced negative connotations such as being 'stuck' or 'left behind'. These labels, directly and indirectly, imply the passivity, lack of agency, backwardness and nonentrepreneurial nature of nonmigrants. Morawka (2013, p. 9) confirms the existing overconcentration on the agency of transmigrants by saying that, even though the importance of another end of a transnational connection is undisputed, 'an almost exclusive focus of a vast volume of studies on immigrants' transnationalism has been on different forms and sociodemographic correlates of these expatriates' engagements in their home countries'.

Describing the context: Central Asian migrants in Russia

Due to the common past as well as ongoing economic and political transformations, post-Soviet countries are tightly connected by large flows of people and capital. Applying the lens of colonialism to the region, the main migration routes still lie along the linkages established during tsarist and Soviet times connecting the postimperial centre and its periphery (Portes, 1995; Schenk, 2018). With its ambition for political and economic domination, Russia has become the main destination for immigration in the region (Eraliev & Urinboev, 2020). As the fourth largest recipient of migrants globally, Russia has been 'one of the world's main migration magnets since the collapse of the Soviet Union' (Eraliev & Urinboev, 2020, p. 258). The overwhelming majority of foreigners in Russia were and are still represented by citizens of former Soviet republics. According to the statistics of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Russian Federation, in 2021, more than 13 million foreign citizens registered with the Russian Immigration Office; in addition to this number, there is an enormous inflow of unregistered migrants (Интернет-портал СНГ, 2022).

The largest share of the migrant community of Russia is formed by nationals of the Central Asian republics of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan (Ryazantzev & Korneev, 2013). Despite the changing character of migration to Russia, it is still predominantly practiced by young, low-skilled males originating from rural areas of Central Asia (Mukomel, 2013). Saodat Olimova, a migration expert from Tajikistan, characterized this situation as a 'muscle drain', as opposed to the 'brain drain', emigration of an educated and skilled labour force (in Denisenko, 2017, p. 132). In addition to this background, another factor that unites Central Asian migrants is the similar challenges they face in Russia, such as securitization and structural and social-ethnic discrimination (Bashirov, 2018). Rarely competing with Russian nationals for qualified positions, Central Asian labour migrants suffer downward labour mobility and have to opt for so-called 3D jobs (dirty, dangerous, difficult) in wholesale and retail trade, construction, services, agriculture and manufacturing (Mukomel, 2013; Zhanaltay, 2018). However, in recent years, many migrants have started their own enterprises in Russia, often in the sectors of their former employment.

Central Asian labour migration to Russia was triggered by a combination of push and pull factors (Schenk, 2018). On the one hand, labour shortages in Russia, higher salaries, visa-free regimes and relative familiarity with the Russian language and culture often make Central Asian citizens opt for Russia as a destination country instead of, for instance, Turkey or Arab states. On the other hand, unemployment, low incomes, corruption, monopolization of certain industries, lack of welfare provision, violations of human rights and political and economic instability serve as push conditions for emigration from Central Asia (Denisenko, 2017; Lipkova et al., 2020; Turaeva, 2018; Zhanaltay, 2018). Poverty is another major issue in the region, especially in rural areas: the share of the population living on less than \$5.5 a day constitutes an overwhelming majority in Uzbekistan (96%), Kyrgyzstan (66%) and Tajikistan (54%) (Lukyanets et al., 2020). A recent study by Lukyanets et al. (2020) also pointed to the importance of environmental factors for emigration from Central Asia: in the absence of combative measures by specialized national agencies, climate change and water shortages severely affect agriculture, which pushes rural populations to leave their traditional places of residence.

In the context of 'nonperforming states, nonfunctioning economies, and low state salaries' (Turaeva, 2018, p. 57), Central Asian citizens are forced to create alternative survival strategies. Many of them have been pushed into entrepreneurship as the only available method of earning a living (Turaeva, 2018). Using the example of mobile entrepreneurs delivering micro-orders between Russia and Uzbekistan, Turaeva (2013) outlines one of these strategies: bypassing states involves informal cross-border business activities regulated by trust networks and unwritten norms. The scholar introduces the term *tirikchilik* (in Uzbek: 'muddling through'), which encompasses strategies for obtaining economic security and welfare outside of the malfunctioning state system. Although it increased substantially after the dissolution of the USSR, informal cross-border entrepreneurship already existed in Soviet times. For instance, the *chelnoki*, or shuttle traders, from Kyrgyzstan selling various, often Western products were crucial economic actors within the Soviet shortage economy (Turaeva, 2013, 2018).

However, because Central Asian republics are among the largest remittance-receiving states globally, their mobile citizens are still considered key agents of transnational entrepreneurship, poverty reduction and development in their home states (Lykhanets et al., 2020). Turaeva (2013) observed that investments that immigrants make in their countries of origin 'play a major role in the maintenance of the transnational economic trust networks' (Turaeva, 2013). Therefore, regional migration studies appear to exhibit the mobility bias prevalent in general migration scholarship; they are preoccupied with migrants as major drivers of cross-border business relations, neglecting the importance of nonmigrants.

DATA AND METHODS

The current article is a part of a larger research project devoted to Central Asian migrant entrepreneurship in Russia; it aims to explore the effects produced by the interaction between migrant entrepreneurship, the Russian opportunity structure and transnationalism. Although the research project adopts a mixed-methods approach, in the current article, only collected qualitative data have been used. The data consist of 36 in-depth semi-structured biographical interviews conducted with Uzbek, Tajik and Kyrgyz migrant entrepreneurs in Moscow and St. Petersburg in the autumn of 2021. Previous research has demonstrated that the majority of Central Asian immigrants reside in urban areas, with one-third concentrated in Moscow and its region (Ryazantsev et al., 2017). Thus, two main business centres in Russia, Moscow and Saint Petersburg, seemed to be the most suitable data collection sites. The number of interviews split almost equally between the two cities. Out of 36 interviewees, 17 reported involvement in transnational business practices; these interviews were analysed in greater depth.

As Nijkamp et al. (2010, p. 372) observed when studying migrant entrepreneurship, 'this type of research is not easy, as it is very difficult to obtain trust, cooperation and proper information from migrant entrepreneurs'. As the main participants' recruitment strategy, respondent-driven (also known as 'snowballing' or 'chain referral') sampling was chosen due to a number of rationales. First, snowballing is regarded as a legitimate recruitment strategy when the study involves hard-to-reach social groups and/or explores sensitive topics. Indeed, Central Asian immigrants represent a hard-to-reach social group, especially when engaging in informal economic activities (Agadjanina & Zotova, 2012). Second, respondent-driven sampling helps to establish trust with interviewees, especially when the latter come from relationship-oriented cultures, which is true in the case of Central Asian nationals (Chandler & Graham, 2010). Finally, the strategy proved its effectiveness in my previous study on African entrepreneurs in Finland; migrant businesspersons are incorporated into wide ethnic business networks and, as a rule, are willing to act as mediators (Yeung, 2019).

The project involved five research assistants from respective ethnic communities; they were trained to effectively recruit research participants. Therefore, interviewees were accessed through my own personal networks and those of the research assistants. The latter often served as mediators between the interviewees and me. The research assistants contacted prospective participants and informed them about the project's aims and questions, their rights (namely, articles 15, 16, 17, 18, 21 and 77 of the General Data Protection Regulation [GDPR]) and the potential risks, often in their native languages. Later, the research assistants introduced me to the entrepreneurs who had agreed to take part in the study. At the end of the interview, an interviewee was asked if he/she knew someone who might be willing to participate in the research. Many gladly shared the contact information of their fellow entrepreneurs.

The main criteria for participants' recruitment were as follows: (1) first-generation migrants (foreign-born individuals); (2) nationality that coincides with ethnicity in this case (Tajik, Uzbek and Kyrgyz nationals born in respective Central Asian republics); (3) ownership of a micro, small- or medium-sized enterprise and (4) the enterprise operates in Moscow or Saint Petersburg. As the first in-depth study on the topic, this research has an explorative character. Diversity in age, gender and industries of operation is considered to be a powerful tool for granting access to various experiences of migrant entrepreneurs in Russia.

Interviews were conducted in the Russian language, audio recorded and transcribed. On average, interviews lasted approximately 30–40 min. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, some of the interviews were conducted online via phone or social media tools such as WhatsApp or Skype. Written or oral consent was obtained from all informants. Considering the increasingly vulnerable position of immigrants in Russia, the safety of the interviewees remained a high priority. The produced project data were processed and stored in line with the University of Bremen and GDPR regulations. Only fully anonymized versions were used for analysis.

The biographical interviews started with questions about reasons for immigration to Russia, touched upon the history of employment in the host state and proceeded to motivations for and the process of establishing one's own enterprise. Among other questions concerning their entrepreneurial journeys, participants were asked whether they had any business links to their home countries or beyond. In the case of affirmative answers, follow-up questions were asked regarding how they searched for business partners, suppliers or clients abroad and what type of resources they received through these transnational channels. Notably, in the vision of the current study, it appears crucial to approach the creation of transnational business relations from the perspective of migrant entrepreneurs. Specifically, it is believed that migrant entrepreneurs are great candidates for assessing the importance of nonmigrants in facilitating cross-border cooperation. Moreover, as the data demonstrated, the interviewees reported a rather passive role in establishing transnational business relations. This self-reporting lowers the chance of social desirability bias intervention with the results of the analysis; as a rule, individuals tend to present themselves as proactive agents when some sort of achievements are involved. Finally, another advantage of this approach is that it provides insights that were not expected but were suggested by the data itself.

The collected data were coded with the help of NVivo software. A mix of theory-driven or deductive and data-based or inductive narrative analysis was conducted. 'People structure their experiences through stories', which helps individuals make sense out of their lives and establish connections to events and other members of society (Sparkes, 2005, p. 191). In the current research, the narrative analysis allows access to the stories that migrant entrepreneurs tell about the establishment and development of their transnational enterprises. To briefly describe the process of analysis, at the first stage, transcripts of the interviews were coded according to the theory of transnationalism with a special focus on the motivations to engage with transnational entrepreneurship, transnational networks and transnational capital. Therefore, when exploring motivations for cross-border business activities, nonmigrants were reported by the interviewees as the main driving forces. Free data-driven codes were created to explore the role of nonmigrant actors in cross-border business activities. At this stage of analysis, in the narratives of the interviewees, nonmigrant suppliers, business partners and clients proved to be crucial, resourceful, risk-taking and cooperative actors. Two main contributions were suggested by the empirical data: initiation of transnational business relations and risk-taking. Thus, issues of risk bearing, a relatively marginal topic in the academic discussion on transnational entrepreneurship, proved to be important for the studied group. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 1.

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Background characteristics

Table 1 summarizes the background characteristics of the interviewees, describes their transnational business relations and presents their industries of operation. Out of 17 interviewees who reported engagement with transnational entrepreneurship, six were female and 11 was male. Their age significantly varied from 26 to 51 years old, with the overwhelming majority being in their 30s. Three research participants run their businesses in St. Petersburg and 14 in Moscow. Nine were originally from Kyrgyzstan, six from Uzbekistan and two from Tajikistan. Most of the interviewees, 13 out of 17, had completed higher education degrees. Regarding background information not included in Table 1, the research participants had been living in Russia for 14 years, on average. They had been engaged in paid employment for 7 years prior to starting their own enterprises. They had a high level of proficiency in the Russian language; as

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Interviewee Number	Gender	Age	Country of origin	City	Education	Industry	Transnational business ties to	Country	Initiator
10	Male	30	Uzbekistan	Moscow	Master's degree	Professional services	Business partner	Uzbekistan	Business partner
11	Female	41	Kyrgyzstan	Moscow	Bachelor's degree	Transportation trade	Suppliers	Kyrgyzstan	Supplier
12	Female	33	Kyrgyzstan	Moscow	Incomplete bachelor's degree	Trade Food and accommodation Professional services	Client Supplier	Kyrgyzstan	Not specified
13	Male	30	Uzbekistan	Moscow	High school	Professional services	Client	Uzbekistan Kazakhstan	Client
14	Female	43	Uzbekistan	Moscow	Middle school	Trade	Client Supplier	Uzbekistan India	Client Business partner
15	Male	38	Kyrgyzstan	Moscow	Bachelor's degree	Sport	Business partner	Kyrgyzstan Kazakhstan	Business partner
16	Male	38	Uzbekistan	Moscow	Bachelor's degree	Food and accommodation	Supplier	Uzbekistan	Not specified
17	Female	35	Uzbekistan	Moscow	Bachelor's degree	Event management	Client	Uzbekistan	Interviewee

Abbreviation: SPB, Saint Petersburg.

assessed by the interviewees themselves, they had from medium to a native command of the Russian language. Most interviewees were married with two or more children.

All research participants had micro- and small-sized enterprises operating in a great variety of industries, including food and accommodation, transportation, trade, professional services and information and communication technology. They reported having transnational business links to suppliers, business partners and clients predominantly in their home states. However, those connections expand beyond their countries of origin and reach Belarus, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Spain, Germany, the United Arab Emirates, China and India (see Table 1). Types of products and services moving within the networks noticeably differ depending on the direction of the trade, either to or from Russia; from Central Asian states, mostly textiles, art, ethnic and bio foods are imported, while from Russia, services in education, consulting and information and communication technology are offered. Moreover, several businesses were involved in transportation and delivery services across the borders. Some research participants (Interviewees 5, 6, 8, 11 and 12) were serial entrepreneurs simultaneously managing several companies in different industries.

Who initiates transnational business relations?

During the interviews, the research participants were asked to describe the process of establishing transnational business relations. Contrary to previous findings, the majority of interviewees stated that, initially, they had no intention of engaging in transnational entrepreneurial activities and did not report recognizing business opportunities or linking them across the borders. Therefore, they were not the ones who mobilized cross-border networks to access advantageous transnational capital. Conversely, in most cases, the initiative to establish transnational business links came from nonmigrant actors in the interviewees' home countries. To be more precise, 10 out of 17 interviewees reported that it was nonmigrants who initiated cross-border business relations (see Table 1). It is important to once again emphasize that this manner of initiation was mentioned by the migrant entrepreneurs themselves, who were assumed to be the main drivers of transnational business relations. However, they reported a relatively passive role in creating cross-border business connections. To substantiate this point, three examples are provided below, in which migrant entrepreneurs described how they were contacted by (1) suppliers, (2) business partners and (3) clients from their countries of origin.

Building transnational networks appears to be one of the strategies used by Central Asian manufacturers and intermediaries that aim at accessing new markets for their goods. The interviewees mentioned that suppliers contacted them and offered their products for use or resale in Russia. For example, male Interviewee 3 has a cross-border delivery service company. From Russia to Kyrgyzstan, they transfer people and parcels; on their way back, various ethnic foods and products are distributed among individual clients as well as the Central Asian catering businesses in Russia. When asked how he established links to the suppliers, the interviewee offered the explanation given below; it both highlights how nonmigrants initiate transnational business relations to earn a living and points to the 'non-performing states' and 'non-functioning economies' of Central Asia, which serve as a push factor for the initiative (Turaeva, 2018, p. 57).

Interviewer: How did you find suppliers there – those who provide you with these products?

Interviewee 3: From Kyrgyzstan? There, as you know, the state is poor, and people have already learned to live by themselves. They have reached out to our guys (aut. - employees of delivery service) themselves. They even help us, they even give us goods for sale, and later we pay them.

Interviewer: Do you mean they give you the goods, you sell them, and then you transfer them the money for the goods?

Interviewee 3: Yes, the money later.

Interviewer: What trust! How big are the companies you order products from?

Interviewee 3: Most of those that reached out to us are small companies from there.

Not only do suppliers reach out to their migrated compatriots in search of new markets, but other enterprises also mobilize transnational connections to enter new business partnerships. For example, male Interviewee 10 owns a consulting firm in Moscow. He provides informational, legal and practical support to Uzbek nationals who would like to obtain a higher education degree on a commercial basis in Russia. He guides them through the process of applying to the universities step by step, assists in preparing the necessary documentation, and even organizes courses to prepare customers for obligatory exams. He has business partners on commission who search for potential clients in Uzbekistan. When asked how he established these business partnerships, the research participant replied:

Interviewee 10: We have a lot of business partners. There are consulting firms that are working specifically in our sphere, I mean those which usually help with admission to universities of the Russian Federation and European countries. They reached out to us, they find clients for us. <...> Today, we cooperate with more than 20 firms <...>.

Interviewer: Your partners, are they in other countries of Central Asia or only in Uzbekistan?

Interviewee 10: No, only in Uzbekistan. <...> We started working with only one company. In addition, next year they already started to recommend us to other firms and companies. <...> And like that, by word of mouth, managers, companies, firms reach out to us, specifically for partnership. You can just sit and filter with whom you want to work, with whom it is profitable, with whom it is not.

Finally, firms and private clients take advantage of their connections to compatriots abroad to access demand for goods and services. For instance, female Interviewee 14 is involved in the resale of various health care products and medications. She buys creams, pills and other health care products in Russia and transfers them to Uzbekistan. Her business is informal if not illegal; the trade of medicines not registered in Uzbekistan is subject to a fine from approximately 1000 to 2000 euros. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, she often travelled to Uzbekistan and personally delivered medications to her clients; at the moment, she cooperated with cross-border delivery companies. The majority of her clients are Uzbek individuals; however, she also provides medicine to small pharmacies and other businesses in Uzbekistan. She explains the process of forming her client base:

Interviewer: How did you find the first customers whom you supply with medications?

Interviewee 14: Medications... There were women who got me engaged with it. Through them there (aut.- in Uzbekistan), people asked my contacts. Like "You are going to Moscow, you can also introduce us, so that she sends medications to us too. She sends them to you, she goes to the pharmacy for medications anyway and then to a delivery company". They took my contacts and reached out to me by phone. They transferred me money, I prepared their order, and went to send it.

Interviewer: Do only individuals or also other businesses order from you?

Interviewee 14: Someone has a pharmacy, someone yes, yes, yes, their own small business.

How are risks distributed?

As the previous section demonstrated, nonmigrant actors initiate transnational business relations and bring in valuable human, social and economic capital. For example, the abovementioned quotes suggest that nonmigrants expand the business networks of migrant entrepreneurs, offer them privileged access to goods and draw on the knowledge of local markets. However, this exchange or joint use of available capital happens under a certain risk distribution. Although it is extremely difficult to weigh the contributions of the two groups in enabling transnational entrepreneurship, nonmigrants nevertheless appear to bear many (if not most) of the crucial associated entrepreneurial risks.

Surely, risk is an integral part of any entrepreneurial activity; however, in the context of two or more transition economies, entrepreneurial risks may significantly increase. Indeed, turbulent markets, political instability, unreliable legal institutions, corruption and a strained international climate make businesspersons especially vulnerable to various market shocks and threats in the post-Soviet region. Despite bilateral trade agreements and the emergence of the Eurasian Economic Union, any international contracts are still highly problematic to enforce. Therefore, this regional example suggests the ambivalence of economic transnationalism; transnational enterprises not only enjoy access to multilocal resources but also become exposed to multilocal risks. Bearing these risks is an important contribution to the facilitation of cross-border business cooperation in the region.

As the data suggest, entering transnational business relations is associated with financial risks for nonmigrants. For example, as male Interviewee 3 in the previous section pointed out, enterprising nonmigrants engage in consignment relationships with migrant entrepreneurs. This relationship represents a clear example of nonmigrant actors' contribution to enabling transnational ventures by bearing significant entrepreneurial risks. The consignment relationship seems to imply more risks for the consignor than for the consignee; the consignor's goods are delivered to a consignee who pays the consignor only, as a rule, for the products sold. Therefore, such a relationship entails indefinite delays in receiving profits and the possibility of goods being damaged, expired or seized, risks assumed solely by the consignor. The consignee, as a rule, does not bear any direct financial risks; however, he/she invests their time, human resources and/or business site space to promote and sell the consignor's goods.

This type of business relationship seems to be popular between nonmigrants and migrant entrepreneurs; other interviewees working in wholesale and retail trade also reported engaging in similar business practices. For example, female Interviewee 4 lives in Moscow and acts as an intermediary; she sells wholesale products of a Kyrgyz textile factory to small stores and bazaar stalls in different Russian cities as well as in Belarus. The interviewee described the consignment relationships that did and still do exist between a factory, an intermediary and points of sale:

Interviewer: So you lent them (aut. – your clients) goods, they did not pay you right away?

Interviewee 4: I did, yes. Yes, it is working in a similar way now as well. I mean, you cannot do a big sale without lending. Big sales surely come with lending. It is exactly the same system here, but it is a bazaar system, the bazaar has always worked with debts.

Interviewer: Do you lend them your products?

Interviewee 4: Yes, you lend them, yes, later on they pay. Respectively, you work in the same way with your own suppliers. <...>

Interviewer: Do you sign some kind of a contract?

Interviewee 4: No, we don't sign any contract.

However, female Interviewee 4 knows the first-hand extreme vulnerabilities that a consignor faces. Before immigration to Russia, she owned a textile production factory in her native Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan. She acted as a consignor to her clients, migrant entrepreneurs in the Cherkizovsky Market. The Cherkizovsky Market has been a centre of international trade in Moscow since the 1990s; thousands of Central Asian migrants have sold their goods there. However, in 2009, according to the official statement of Russian authorities, due to various violations and smuggling of goods, the decision was made to shut the market down. This was followed by the violent destruction of more than 6000 points of sale. The closure produced a domino effect of vulnerability. Having lost all goods during the shutdown, the clients could not repay Interviewee 4 back. Ultimately, she went bankrupt. It partially pushed her to emigrate to Russia to find a well-paid job and cover debts.

Along with profit maximization (mentioned above by Interviewee 4), another reason for nonmigrants' engagement in consignment relationships might reside in the size and limited cash on hand of migrant companies. Indeed, Central Asian migrant enterprises in Russia are micro and small-size ventures with limited capital. Moreover, they face multiple barriers to obtaining credit in Russia, which significantly impacts their prospects for growth. Therefore, migrant entrepreneurs are often simply unable to bear expenses associated with transnational entrepreneurship; they might not have enough cash on hand to immediately pay for products provided by their suppliers. In this situation, the consignment relationship is often the only type of business cooperation that can enable transnational entrepreneurship.

For example, female Interviewee 11 has a cross-border delivery service company in Moscow, similar to the one owned by Interviewee 3 in St. Petersburg. She also mentioned that the initiative to start transnational business relations came from suppliers in her home country. She described the process of establishing cooperation in which, due to her lack of funding, the consignment relationship seemed to be the only option available:

Interviewee 11: They simply found us, there are not so many of them, so... <...> At first, they did not trust us, we asked them to lend us products, or at least that we could postpone the payment, because we didn't have much money, such a large amount... They did not agree at first, but in the end, when they saw our results, they already started cooperating. They helped a lot with advertising.

Interviewer: And how many suppliers do you have in Kyrgyzstan?

Interviewee 11: There are seven big ones, there are more small ones, I just do not count the small ones.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The contributions of the existing research are multifold; along with improving our understanding of transnational entrepreneurship, it also provides deeper insights into the broader phenomena of transnationalism and migration. This study was intended to facilitate the growing interest in immobility in migration studies. It aimed to unveil the existing mobility bias in transnational entrepreneurship and to construct a more balanced and nuanced view of transnational entrepreneurship, in which academic attention is shared between both stasis and movement (Erdal, 2021; Schewel, 2020; Schiller & Salazar, 2013). Thus, more generally, the research supports the claim that mobility and immobility are integrally intertwined and mutually conditioned (e.g., Erdal, 2021).

To date, the relevant scholarship seems to be preoccupied with the agency of immigrants, ignoring the vital contributions of nonmigrants in enabling transnational entrepreneurship (Schewel, 2020). Therefore, this study challenges the existing perception of migrant entrepreneurs as major drivers of cross-border business cooperation (e.g., Honig, 2020) as well as the portrayal of nonmigrant actors as being of secondary importance, inert and nonentrepreneurial (Stockdale & Haartsen, 2018). In this regard, this study calls for a revision of the existing definitions of transnational entrepreneurship, introduced by Portes et al. (2002), Chen and Tan (2009) and Drori et al. (2009). Indeed, the very term

'transnational *migrant* entrepreneurship' reaffirms the central role of immigrants in cross-border business relations. To counteract this, transnational entrepreneurship should be approached as a result of joint efforts of both mobile and sedentary populations.

Drawing on qualitative data collected from Central Asian migrant entrepreneurs in Russia, this article demonstrated the utmost importance of nonmigrants in the creation and development of transnational enterprises. Migrant entrepreneurs reported a rather passive role in establishing cross-border business relations, highlighting that nonmigrant actors were the major driving forces of transnational business cooperation. First, nonmigrants acted as initiators of cross-border entrepreneurship; they recognized business opportunities, established new or mobilized existing networks and, therefore, took advantage of transnational capital. This contrasts with the findings of previous studies that assigned those activities exclusively to migrant entrepreneurs (e.g., Drori et al., 2009; Duan et al., 2021; Sommer, 2020).

Furthermore, transnational entrepreneurship may have been impossible without nonmigrants' willingness to assume part of the associated risks (Yeung, 2002). The instability of post-Soviet transition economies points to a certain ambivalence of regional economic transnationalism that is characterized by both increased opportunities and risks. Residents of the Central Asian republics engage in particularly risky cross-border consignment relationships; at times, this is the only option that enables transnational entrepreneurship. This study slightly touched upon probable causal factors behind risk-taking behaviour. Transnational entrepreneurship may be used by nonmigrant populations (1) as an alternative survival strategy in the context of poorly working economies and malfunctioning states (Turaeva, 2013) and/or (2) as a well-being improvement strategy and an alternative to emigration (Carling et al., 2021).

The abovementioned findings suggest that migration is a phenomenon whose effects may be distributed over both mobile and nonmigrant populations. Often approached as an individual choice, migration and its impacts, however, spread far beyond its agents. As the data demonstrated, emigration of a compatriot may allow nonmigrants to gain access to transnational social and economic fields. Nevertheless, not only do migrants have a crucial influence over communities in their home states (e.g., Morawska, 2013), but nonmigrants can also shape the lives of their compatriots abroad. Sedentary actors may have a significant impact on migrants' business plans and incomes. It bears repeating that transnational entrepreneurship would remain inaccessible to Central Asian migrants in Russia without the role played by nonmigrants in undertaking a share of the associated entrepreneurial risks.

As a final remark, it should be carefully noted that this study in no way attempts to diminish or question the agency and crucial contributions of immigrants in enabling transnational entrepreneurship. Rather, it calls for a more balanced and inclusive vision of how transnational phenomena occur. Future research should continue exploring the interdependency between mobility and immobility. It could identify other forms of mobility bias and the ways in which it affects our understanding of transnational social and economic phenomena. Perspectives of nonmigrant individuals should be included in studies to counterbalance and/or complement migrants' standpoints. Moreover, comparative studies regarding the entrepreneurial activities of migrants versus nonmigrants could enrich our understanding of different types of transnational practices. Finally, the conditions under which sedentary populations refer to transnational fields should receive due attention. Similar research may assist in generating a more complex yet more precise understanding of transnationalism and migration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This publication has been produced within the ITN 'MARKETS', which is funded by an EU-MSCA grant (Horizon 2020, grant agreement No: 861034). Any views expressed are those of the author and do not reflect the official policy or position of any institution or funding body.

Open access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Research data are not shared.

ETHICS STATEMENT

The research received the approval of the Ethics Committee of the Research Centre for East European Studies, the University of Bremen.

REFERENCES

- Agadjanian, V., & Zotova, N. (2012). Sampling and surveying hard-to-reach populations for demographic research: A study of female labor migrants in Moscow, Russia. *Demographic Research*, 26(5), 131–150.
- Ambrosini, M. (2012). Migrants' entrepreneurship in transnational social fields: Research in the Italian context. *International Review of Sociology*, 22(2), 273–292.
- Bagwell, S. (2015). Transnational entrepreneurship amongst Vietnamese businesses in London. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 41(2), 329–349. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369183X.2014.907739>
- Bagwell, S. (2018). From mixed embeddedness to transnational mixed embeddedness: An exploration of Vietnamese businesses in London. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 24(1), 104–120.
- Bashirov, G. (2018). Between strong and weak securitization: A comparative study of Russian and Turkish approaches to migration from Central Asia. In L. Marlene & S. Caress (Eds.), *Eurasia on the move: Interdisciplinary approaches to a dynamic migration region* (pp. 13–26). The George Washington University, Central Asia Program.
- Batista, C., & Umblijs, J. (2014). Migration, risk attitudes, and entrepreneurship: Evidence from a representative immigrant survey. *IZA Journal of Migration*, 3(17), 1–25.
- Brzozowski, J., Cucculelli, M., & Surdej, A. (2014). Transnational ties and performance of immigrant entrepreneurs: The role of home-country conditions. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 26(7–8), 546–573.
- Brzozowski, J., Cucculelli, M., & Surdej, A. (2017). The determinants of transnational entrepreneurship and transnational ties' dynamics among immigrant entrepreneurs in ICT sector in Italy. *International Migration*, 55(3), 105–125.
- Carling, J., Erdal, M. B., & Talleraas, C. (2021). Living in two countries: Transnational living as an alternative to migration. *Population, Space and Place*, 27(5), e2471.
- Chandler, J. D., & Graham, J. L. (2010). Relationship-oriented cultures, corruption, and international marketing success. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 92, 251–267.
- Chen, W., & Tan, J. (2009). Understanding transnational entrepreneurship through a network lens: Theoretical and methodological considerations. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(5), 1079–1091.
- Collyer, M. (2007). In-between places: Trans-Saharan transit migrants in Morocco and the fragmented journey to Europe. *Antipode*, 39(4), 668–690.
- David, A., Schäfer, S., & Terstriep, J. (2021). *Characteristics of migrant entrepreneurs: Asset in times of crisis?* *Forschung Aktuell*, No. 01/2021. Institut Arbeit und Technik (IAT).
- Denisenko, M. (2017). Migration to Russia and the current economic crisis. In A. Pikulicka-Wilczewska & G. Uehling (Eds.) *Migration and the Ukraine crisis: A two-country perspective* (129–148). E-International Relations.
- Drori, I., Honig, B., & Wright, M. (2009). Transnational entrepreneurship: An emergent field of study. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(5), 1001–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2009.00332.x>
- Duan, C., Kotev, B., & Sandhu, K. (2021). Transnational immigrant entrepreneurship: Effects of home-country entrepreneurial ecosystem factors. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 27(3), 711–729.
- Elo, M. (2014). Diaspora networks in international business and transnational entrepreneurship—A literature review. *ZenTra Working Paper in Transnational Studies*, 40, <http://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2518428>
- Eraliev, S., & Urinboyev, R. (2020). Precarious times for Central Asian migrants in Russia. *Current History*, 119(819), 258–263.
- Erdal, M. B. (2021). Migrants' multifocal sedentarism: Ambivalent belonging and desired recognition in transnational social fields connecting Pakistan and Norway. *Journal of Intercultural Studies*, 42(5), 643–659.
- Filion, L.-J. (2021). Defining the entrepreneur. In L. Dana (Ed.) *World encyclopedia of entrepreneurship* (pp. 72–83). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Harima, A. (2014). Network dynamics of descending diaspora entrepreneurship: multiple case studies with Japanese entrepreneurs in emerging economies. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Innovation*, 10(4), 65–92.
- Harima, A., & Baron, T. (2020). Is this transnational entrepreneurship? Five cases in which it is hard to say 'yes' or 'no'. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Emerging Economies*, 6(1), 12–40.
- Honig, B. (2020). Exploring the intersection of transnational, ethnic, and migration entrepreneurship. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 46(10), 1974–1990.
- Levitt, P. (2001). Transnational migration: Taking stock and future directions. *Global Networks*, 1(3), 195–216.

- Levitt, P., & Schiller, N. G. (2004). Conceptualizing simultaneity: A transnational social field perspective on society. *International Migration Review*, 38(3), 1002–1039.
- Lipkova, L., Broskova, K., & Baleha, A. (2020). Labour migration in Central Asia. Economic factors of influence. *Economic Annals-XXI*, 184(7–8), 38–48.
- Lukyanets, A., Ryazantsev, S., Moiseeva, E., & Manshin, R. (2020). The economic and social consequences of environmental migration in the Central Asian countries. *Central Asia and the Caucasus*, 21(1), 142–156.
- Lundberg, H., & Rehnfors, A. (2018). Transnational entrepreneurship: Opportunity identification and venture creation. *Journal of International Entrepreneurship*, 16, 150–175.
- Menzies, T. V., Brenner, G. A., & Filion, L. J. (2003). Social capital, networks and ethnic minority entrepreneurs: Transnational entrepreneurship and bootstrap capitalism. In H. Etamad & R. Wright (Eds.), *Globalization and entrepreneurship: Policy and strategy perspectives* (pp. 125–151). Edward Elgar,.
- Morawska, E. (2013). The impact of past and present immigrants' transnational engagements on their home-country localities: Exploring an under-investigated aspect of transnationalism-migration relationship. *Studia Migracyjne—Przegląd Polonijny*, 1(147), 7–31.
- Mukomel, V. (2013). Labour mobility of migrants from CIS countries in Russia. *Central and Eastern European Migration Review*, 2(2), 21–38.
- Nijkamp, P., Sahin, M., & Baycan-Levent, T. (2010). Migrant entrepreneurship and new urban economic opportunities: Identification of critical success factors by means of qualitative pattern recognition analysis. *Tijdschrift Voor Economische en Sociale Geografie*, 101(4), 371–391.
- Ojo, S. (2012). Ethnic enclaves to diaspora entrepreneurs: A critical appraisal of Black British Africans' transnational entrepreneurship in London. *Journal of African Business*, 13(2), 145–156.
- Portes, A. (Ed.) (1995). *Economic sociology of immigration: The essays on networks, ethnicity and entrepreneurship*. Russel Sage Foundation.
- Portes, A., Guarnizo, L. E., & Haller, W. J. (2002). Transnational entrepreneurs: An alternative form of immigrant economic adaptation. *American Sociological Review*, 67, 278–298.
- Pruthi, S., Basu, A., & Wright, M. (2018). Ethnic ties, motivations, and home country entry strategy of transnational entrepreneurs. *Journal of International Entrepreneurship*, 16(2), 210–243.
- Ryazantsev, S., & Korneev, O. (2013). Russia and Kazakhstan in Eurasian migration system: Development trends, socio-economic consequences of migration and approaches to regulation. Migration Policy Centre, CARIM-East Research Report, 2013/44. <http://hdl.handle.net/1814/29930>
- Ryazantsev, S., Bogdanov, I., Dobrokhleb, V., & Lukyanets, A. (2017). Migration from Central Asian countries to Russia and Kazakhstan in the context of integration processes in the Eurasian Economic Union format. *Central Asia and The Caucasus*, 18(1), 39–49.
- Salazar, N. B., & Smart, A. (2011). Anthropological Takes on (Im)Mobility. *Identities*, 18(6), I–IX.
- Sandoz, L., Mittmasser, C., Riaño, Y., & Piguet, E. (2021). A review of transnational migrant entrepreneurship: Perspectives on unequal spatialities. *ZFW – Advances in Economic Geography*, 66, 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zfw-2021-0004>
- Schenk, C. (2018). Eurasian migration studies: Challenges and developments. In M. Laruelle & C. Schenk (Eds.), *Eurasia on the move: Interdisciplinary approaches to a dynamic migration region* (pp. 9–11). The George Washington University, Central Asia Program.
- Schewel, K. (2020). Understanding immobility: Moving beyond the mobility bias in migration studies. *International Migration Review*, 54(2), 328–355. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0197918319831952>
- Schiller, N. G., & Salazar, N. B. (2013). Regimes of mobility across the globe. *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, 39(2), 183–200.
- Schiller, N. G., Basch, L., & Blanc-Szanton, C. (1992). Transnationalism: A new analytic framework for understanding migration. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 645(1), 1–24.
- Sinkovics, N., & Reuber, A. R. (2021). Beyond disciplinary silos: A systematic analysis of the migrant entrepreneurship literature. *Journal of World Business*, 56(4), 101223. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zfw-2021-0004>
- Sommer, E. (2020). Transnational entrepreneurial activities (TEA). *Social capital as a resource for migrant entrepreneurship* (pp. 237–281). Springer VS. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-29141-9_8
- Sparkes, A. C. (2005). Narrative analysis: Exploring the whats and hows of personal stories. *Qualitative Research in Health Care*, 1(1), 191–209.
- Stockdale, A., & Haartsen, T. (2018). Editorial introduction: Putting rural stayers in the spotlight. *Population, Space and Place*, 24(4), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/psp.2124>
- Tedeschi, M., Vorobeva, E., & Jauhiainen, J. S. (2020). Transnationalism: Current debates and new perspectives. *GeoJournal*, 87, 603–619. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-020-10271-8>
- Turavaeva, R. (2013). Post-Soviet uncertainties: Micro-orders of Central Asian migrants in Russia. *Inner Asia*, 15(2), 272–292.

- Turaeva, R. (2018). Informal economies in the post-Soviet space: Post-Soviet Islam and its role in ordering entrepreneurship in Central Asia. *Central Asian Affairs*, 5(1), 57–75.
- Yeung, H. W.-C. (2002). Entrepreneurship in international business: An institutional perspective. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 19, 29–61.
- Zhanaltay, Z. (2018). Social remittance dynamics in Central Asia: Potential and limitations. In M. Laruelle & C. Schenk (Eds.), *Eurasia on the move: Interdisciplinary approaches to a dynamic migration region* (pp. 160–67). The George Washington University, Central Asia Program.
- Интернет-портал СНГ (2022). Миграционная ситуация в Российской Федерации за 2021 год. <https://e-cis.info/cooperation/3823/99651/>

How to cite this article: Vorobeva, E. (2022). Overcoming the mobility bias in transnational entrepreneurship. *Global Networks*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/glob.12424>